

Drexel University

Letter to Carlsberg

COIL Group

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MKTG-368-001

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9 December 2021

INTRODUCTION

Carlsberg Group is a globally operated brewery firm based out of Denmark with over 500 subsidiaries and a long history of creating craft beers. In 2011, the firm introduced the Droughtmaster system as an alternative means of beer delivery within a bar, pub or restaurant setting. The system is presented as a much more sustainable option stemming from a multitude of its innovations. Not only are there less emissions from the release of excess CO₂ and the elimination of insurmountable quantities of water waste stemming from the cleaning of traditional steel kegs, the system uses plastic kegs as an alternative as they are recyclable.

Carlsberg wants to ensure that the DroughtMaster launch within the US marketplace is successful. It becomes incredibly important to see if both the B2B and B2C markets see the benefits of switching to a plastic alternative keg system within the expectations and wishes of its implementation; this is especially the case in preparing to launch in an international market. If American consumer behavior and interest are not equivalent to the sales potential, it does not make sense to launch the product within the market. One must take into consideration several factors: the cultural norms of the market and the effect they have on potential consumer interest, current market conditions and the product's applicability to be effective within the marketplace. If American consumer and business owner behavior and interest are not equivalent to the sales potential, it does not make sense to launch the product within the market. Doing so in light of contradicting evidence would result in wasted time, energy and resources.

Rather than conducting research and compiling data via secondary sources, our team dove into discovering what insight real beer consumers and business owners had to say about the DroughtMaster system and if this would be of interest to them. Within this report, we will dive into the methodology used to gather our data, the information itself and our recommendations to Carlsberg.

METHODOLOGY

The project's main objective was to determine whether or not Carlsberg should expand its DraughtMaster® system to the United States, and if so, how they could best segment its value to ensure a successful launch. Our research sought to understand the opinions of individual beer drinkers as well as restaurant and bar owners who served beer on tap regarding their opinions on distributing, handling, and serving beer, and also their attitudes toward sustainable business practices. More specifically, we sought answers to the following questions:

1. *What is the perception (B2C and B2B) about introducing a plastic-based system (Draughtmasters®) to fight pollution and benefit the environment?*

2. *How do B2B and B2C customers reconcile the potential conflict between using plastics and being sustainable?*
3. *What do businesses that currently use Draughtmasters® (bars, pubs, and restaurants) think of the system?*
4. *What changes, if any, need to be made to Draughtmasters® if it is to be launched in the United States?*

To do this, extensive qualitative research was conducted through one-on-one in-person interviews with consumers and business owners here in the United States, as well as in Germany, where the DraughtMaster® system has already been successfully implemented. The structure of the interviews followed an “hourglass” format outlined below, where both general and specific questions were asked to gauge the attitudes of our participants. The DraughtMaster® system was also introduced and explained during the “Concept Testing” stage, where we asked specific questions to understand the respondent’s reactions.

Two rounds of interviews were conducted - First, with specific beer-drinking consumers. Ten interviews were held here in the United States, and ten more in Germany, for a total of twenty B2C interviews. Various open-ended questions were asked about the individual’s drinking habits, their attitudes toward sustainable businesses, and their likes and dislikes about Carlsberg’s DraughtMaster® system. The second round consisted of eleven in-person B2B interviews (six held in the United States and five in Germany). Participants consisted of business owners, restaurant and bar managers, bartenders, and waiters and servers. We were most interested in their insights regarding storing and distributing beer, understanding what difficulties they had in doing so, as well as their opinions about environmentalism and sustainability. More specifically, we sought to understand how they would reconcile the conflict between using plastic kegs

instead of traditional metal ones. Like before, we also introduced the DraughtMaster® system to understand their general perceptions, their likes and dislikes, and their willingness to implement it. All participant's responses were recorded and analyzed to examine the results and trends which are explained below.

FINDINGS

Both consumers in the USA and Germany expressed an openness to the DraughtMaster®, as long as the taste does not lose its quality. During the B2C interview conducted in the United States, the interviewee expressed that “if {the DraughtMaster® system} allows the beer industry to move forward in terms of sustainability and it does not detract from the taste of beer, I’d go right for it.” The interviewee from Germany expressed the same thoughts and explained how “the most important thing {is} how the beer tastes... expecting that it is cold {and} not too sparkling.” The interviewee went on to question how the DraughtMaster® system manages to keep beer cold in the plastic kegs. While our interviewees presented concerns relating to the taste, they made it clear that if there is not a difference, they would be interested in the DraughtMaster® system.

Consumers in the United States and Germany were skeptical of the process of the DraughtMaster®. The interviewee from the United States explained how the DraughtMaster® system would be new for brewers, restaurants, pubs, and consumers and, “would be a learning curve and a shared experience for all.” Consumers in the United States seemed to doubt how single-use plastic is a better alternative to traditional kegs, which can be upcycled. Immediately after showing the United States interviewee a video explaining the DraughtMaster® system, they said “I wouldn’t trust a company per se just on their word of mouth, I would love to know the statistics behind why it would be more sustainable. Metal kegs can of course be used and reused and then also upcycled for so many other things, while a plastic keg at the end of the day is still plastic.” The interviewee from Germany also had doubts relating to the recycling process. This interviewee raised many questions, including “How much energy does the recycling process cost? If you want to recycle every one of those small kegs or cans, is it really that more effective or efficient in terms of climate and sustainability to always recycle them after a single use?” They went on to explain how, “you do not have to recycle metal kegs, you just have to wash them out and you can fill them up again.” The B2B interviewee from Germany felt that he could not convince his customers of the benefits of the DraughtMaster® system if he himself did not believe in the methodology. We found that both consumers in the United States and Germany are interested in understanding the research and data behind this new process to better understand its sustainability impact.

Businesses in the USA are unprepared to switch to sustainable options due to obstacles including time, money, and infrastructure, while businesses in Germany have already implemented sustainable options. Within our B2B interview, the owner expressed that they already practice sustainable measures, so he is not reluctant to adopt sustainable methods. The

B2B interviewee had prior experience with the DraughtMaster® system and thought it was a great sustainable option for bars. Although, the interviewee from Germany posed similar concerns to businesses in the USA relating to price. When asked why the bar owner had decided against the system, he explained that they “decided against the DraughtMaster® because first of all it's too expensive and steel kegs are more practical, you don't have to change as often.” While sustainability is a concern for many bars, restaurants, and breweries, we found these businesses to ultimately choose a more feasible pricing option over sustainability.

RECOMMENDATIONS

After examining the details of the interviews conducted in both the United States and Germany, it is clear that small changes to the process of the DraughtMaster® system could have exceptional results on the success of the product. One of the main concerns from both the United States B2C and Germany B2B interviewees was that the DraughtMaster® system would ultimately alter the taste of the beer. Since the system itself is made of plastic, one recommendation is to coat the inside of the system with a metal-like plastic. Recent research at Yale University has helped create bulk metallic glasses (BMGs). According to Kit Eaton BMGs, “are alloys of metals where the structure is randomly arranged, giving them some of the material powers of glass, and some traditional metals...that can be blow-molded into shapes that are easily created using plastic or glass, but impossible using regular metals. They have the strength, resistance to impact, and durability of metal” (Eaton). If the DraughtMaster® system uses a BMG coating and goes through a thorough trial and error testing process, it is less likely for the taste of the beer to be altered.

Another concern brought up by the interviewee from the United States was the learning curve that restaurant and bar owners and employees will face when implementing the DraughtMaster® system. In order to avoid any confusion when using the new system, Carlsberg could potentially create a collection or series of training videos that will be provided to owners when the new system is purchased. The videos will provide an in depth explanation and tutorials on how to use the DraughtMaster® system properly. The video series will provide restaurant and bar employees with statistics of how the product is more sustainable. In addition to this, one recommendation that could be made is to alter the marketing campaign of the DraughtMaster® system. When marketing the product to potential buyers, it is vital that marketing campaigns include statistics and testimonials from users on how the DraughtMaster® system ultimately improves their business. Surveys could be filled out by users of the product before it officially launches and will be a part of the overall campaign. This will create an emotional appeal to prospective consumers and will add more meaning to the campaign overall. In terms of expenses, Carlsberg's main outgoing payments would be for advertisements. Advertisements for the campaign could be seen across social media, streaming services, and television. For social media advertisements alone, a minimum monthly budget of \$300-\$900 should be set aside in order to place ads on all of the major social media platforms. If the budget allows, Carlsberg could work

with a social media marketing agency to help boost the success of the campaign and integration into the United States.

This also leads to another recommendation that can be proposed. The DraughtMaster® system can be targeted to bars and restaurants in locations that practice sustainability so there is a cohesiveness to the brand. As shown in the findings, it was clear that businesses in the US were not ready to implement sustainable practices. It is a common trend that restaurant owners will choose the cheaper product to save money, rather than splurge on the more expensive and sustainable methods. If the DraughtMaster® system began its marketing efforts to restaurants and bars in places like Portland, Seattle, or Washington D.C., other cities will see its success and want to apply the DraughtMaster® system in their establishment. This will lead to favorable outcomes across the United States.

Works Cited

Eaton, Kit. "Metals Like Plastics: Meet the Super Material That Could Change Gadgets." *Fast Company*, Fast Company, 30 July 2012, <https://www.fastcompany.com/1733096/metals-plastics-meet-supermaterial-could-change-gadgets>.